

A Time-Step-Based Neural Network Framework for Modeling Chaotic Dynamics in Multi-Pendulum and Biological Systems

1st Vasista Ramachandrani
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
vasista.ramachandrani@students.asdrp.org

2nd Sai Hruday Reddy Nara
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
sai.nara@students.asdrp.org

3rd Geo Lalu
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
geo.lalu@students.asdrp.org

4th Prashanth Prabhala*
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
prashanth.prabhala@gmail.com

5th Sabrina Yang
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
sabrina.yang@students.asdrp.org

6th Mohit Ramesh Kumar
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
mohit.kumar@students.asdrp.org

7th Aarjav Jain
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
aarjav.jain@students.asdrp.org

8th Pratham Mehta
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
pratham.mehta@students.asdrp.org

9th Hanyu Koo
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
hanyu.koo@students.asdrp.org

10th Jason Damonte
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
jason.damonte@students.asdrp.org

11th Marx Akl
Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering
Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program
Fremont, USA
marx.akl@asdrp.org

Abstract—Chaotic systems are highly sensitive to initial conditions and external influences, making them difficult to predict yet critically important across disciplines such as prediction of brainwaves in medicine, modulating protein production in biology, gene regulation networks, and robotics in bioengineering. In this study, we explore the predictability of a classical chaotic

system, the multi-pendulum, intending to establish it as a basis for future explorations into specialized cases of the results of this paper, using ten different machine learning models and neural networks. We begin by generating synthetic data representing the angles of the pendulum over time using the Runge-Kutta method for solving fourth-order differential equations. Initially, a single-step sliding window approach was employed, where the model predicted the 50th time step after training on steps 0

through 49. To better capture the chaotic nature of the system, we later adopted a time-step-based approach, training on a wide range of initial angles and testing on unseen, interpolated initial conditions to evaluate generalization. We also assessed system stability using Lyapunov exponents. Our results showed that for the double pendulum, the Long Short-Term Memory network outperformed other models in both the sliding window and time-step methods, under both frictional and frictionless conditions. For the triple pendulum, the Vanilla Recurrent Neural Network was most effective in the sliding window setup, while the Gated Recurrent Unit excelled in the time-step approach. However, in scenarios with a predefined frictional constant, the Long Short-Term Memory model again proved to be the most robust.

Index Terms—Chaotic Systems, Multi-Pendulum, Differential Equations, Runge-Kutta (ODE-RK4), Time-Series Forecasting, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), MLP Regressor, Lyapunov Exponents, Friction Modeling, Nonlinear Dynamics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Chaotic systems [1], characterized by extreme sensitivity to initial conditions, permeate both natural and engineered domains. They appear prominently in weather patterns [2], financial markets [3], and **particularly in biological and biomedical contexts** [4]. For instance, gene regulatory networks can display oscillatory or near-chaotic gene expression levels, while neural circuits may exhibit highly non-linear dynamics. Such complex systems depend on a variety of factors: time, initial conditions, changing conditions, etc [5],[6]. For example, a real world situation involving flight paths [7] has many variables at play: weather, traffic of fliers, engine health, and many more, making it extremely difficult to predict or even model them. Particularly however, accurate modeling and prediction of such complex behaviors is crucial in bioinformatics: identifying early-stage irregularities in physiological systems or pinpointing critical intervention points in disease progression depend on robust computational strategies.

In this paper, we focus on the multi-pendulum system (e.g., double or triple pendulum) as an archetypal test bed for chaotic dynamics. Although mechanical in nature, multi-pendula offer a tractable proxy for multi-component biological systems that exhibit intricate oscillatory behavior. The simplest case is the double pendulum, one mass attached to an immovable pivot, with a second mass attached to the first mass’s endpoint [8], as illustrated in Fig. 3. The triple pendulum [9] adds a third mass, increasing the dimensionality of chaos. Small perturbations in initial angles (or, by analogy, biological parameters) can lead to vastly different trajectories.

Fig. 2 displays typical chaotic motions for the double and triple pendulum over. Given this sensitive dependence on initial angles, these systems serve as excellent testbeds to explore methods for modeling non-linear dynamics.

Configuration Vector for Double Pendulum: We define $\mathbf{V} = [\theta_1, u_1, \theta_2, u_2]$ where $u_1 = \frac{d\theta_1}{dt}$ and $u_2 = \frac{d\theta_2}{dt}$. Let

$$c = \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2), \quad s = \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2).$$

Then the governing equations [10] are (in *compact* form):

Fig. 1. An illustration of the double/triple pendulum with angles, masses, and lengths labeled.

Fig. 2. Animation snapshots of the double and triple pendulum across 10s of motion. Both exhibit significant chaotic behavior, particularly at higher initial angles. Made using differential equations from cloud4science et al. [10]

$$\frac{du_1}{dt} = \frac{m_2 g \sin(\theta_2) c - m_2 s (L_1 u_1^2 + L_2 u_2^2) - (m_1 + m_2) g \sin(\theta_1)}{L_1 (m_1 + m_2 s^2)} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{du_2}{dt} = \frac{(m_1 + m_2) (L_1 u_1^2 s - g \sin(\theta_1) + g \sin(\theta_2) c) + m_2 L_2 u_2^2 s c}{L_2 (m_1 + m_2 s^2)} \quad (2)$$

An infinite N number of pendulums can be added to these differential equations, but computation gets significantly more complex as N increases [11].

We solve Eqs. (1)–(2) numerically via Runge–Kutta 4th Order Method [12] to generate synthetic angle trajectories. *For the triple pendulum, the equations are significantly more complex and are therefore provided in the Electronic Supplementary Information.*

By treating the pendulum angles as analogous to “states” in a biological or other complex system, we can systematically investigate the role of friction (akin to damping in real physiological processes [13]) and other parameters. After assembling a substantial time-series dataset of angles, we apply various machine learning (ML) and neural network (NN) models—particularly recurrent architectures like LSTM [14] to predict future states from historical data. The core challenge lies in whether these methods can capture the extreme non-linearity and divergence inherent in chaotic pendulum trajectories.

Our contributions include:

- A time-step-based prediction approach that generalizes beyond a single set of initial conditions, enabling robust modeling of chaotic regimes.
- Demonstration that recurrent neural networks (e.g., LSTM) significantly outperform classical methods (e.g., Autoregressive [15]) for pendulum angle prediction.
- Application of Lyapunov exponents [16] and eigenvalue analyses to characterize stability in the multi-pendulum system, illuminating how friction and parameter choices impact chaos.

By bridging mechanical chaos with biological analogies, we show how these data-driven methods may extend to other oscillatory phenomena—e.g., irregular cardiac rhythms, neural spiking, or gene expression cycles—where non-linear interactions are prevalent. These mappings highlight how chaos theory and predictive modeling can contribute to biomedical diagnostics and personalized medicine. In subsequent sections, we detail our methodology, experimental setup, comparative model performance, and the broader implications of chaos modeling in a bioinformatics context.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Data Generation and Preprocessing

We generated synthetic time-series data for both the double and triple pendulum using standard fourth-order Runge–Kutta numerical integration (ODE-RK4). For the double pendulum, the classical equations of motion (Eqs. (1)–(2) in the main text) were integrated under two conditions: (i) frictionless and (ii) including a damping term for friction [17]. The triple pendulum equations were similarly integrated based on formulations in [18].

Preprocessing/Setup: In this study, two training approaches were tested, one training on a single, fixed angle and another training on multiple initial angles and predicting an “in-between” unknown angle. **Information on each approach is elaborated on in detail in (B).**

- *Time Interval of Recorded Motion:* For the first training approach, a long simulation interval (up to 1000 s, step of 0.001 s) was used to explore chaotic behavior. For the final multi-angle studies, a shorter interval (e.g., 10 s, step of 0.001 s) was chosen to allow multiple runs at distinct initial angles without overflow. For both approaches, the **ODE-RK4 method** was used to solve the equations of motion.
- *Arrays:* The position vectors of the pendulum at every step of the motion were stored in 2D NumPy arrays (large array for storing all data points, smaller separate arrays for each angle (θ_1, θ_2) or $(\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3)$ [19] for subsequent feature engineering. Normalization (MinMax) was applied to reduce outlier impact [20].

After solving the differential equations using the ODE-RK4 method, we created an animation using Matplotlib to plot the double and triple pendulum data points at a steep

Initial conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} g &= 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 \\ l_1 &= 1 \text{ m} \\ l_2 &= 1 \text{ m} \\ m_1 &= 1 \text{ kg} \\ m_2 &= 1 \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$

Key - g: Gravitational Constant on Earth ($\frac{m}{s^2}$), L: Length of Pendulum 1/2 (meters), m: mass of Pendulum 1/2 (kg), y: position (given recursively), k: Approximations of the derivative at different points within our iteration, h: Size of each step

Fig. 3. Initial Conditions and ODE-RK4 Algorithm

Fig. 4. RK4 Simulation Results for Double Pendulum Dynamics. Numerical solutions using the 4th-order Runge–Kutta method (RK4) showing the angular evolution of θ_1 and θ_2 over the interval $t \in (0, 1000)$.

The system is simulated under standard gravity ($g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$) with the following initial conditions:

Case 6A: $l_1 = 1 \text{ m}$, $l_2 = 2 \text{ m}$, $m_1 = 1 \text{ kg}$, $m_2 = 1 \text{ kg}$, $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$, $\theta_2 = 90^\circ$.

Case 6B (Modified): $l_1 = 1 \text{ m}$, $l_2 = 2 \text{ m}$, $m_1 = 2 \text{ kg}$, $m_2 = 1 \text{ kg}$, $\theta_1 = 60^\circ$, $\theta_2 = 90^\circ$.

angle ($[120^\circ, 120^\circ]$) to visualize the trajectory graph over a 10-second interval (see Figures 4A, 4B).

Due to the high sensitivity to initial conditions (see Figure 3), we tested different starting values to observe how they influenced the resulting trajectories of the double pendulum.

Parameter Variation: We systematically varied the initial angles (θ_1, θ_2) in the double pendulum or $(\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3)$ in the triple pendulum. For each chosen tuple, we integrated for N time steps (e.g., $N = 2000$), producing multiple trajectories that spanned a range of chaotic regimes [21].

B. Model Training Approaches

1) *Sliding Window:* Initially, we employed a single-step sliding window [22] over a single set of angles, where sequences of size W (e.g., 50 consecutive time steps) trained the model to predict the next step $W + 1$. For this method, neural networks were given the position of the pendulum as input features, θ_1, θ_2 for double pendulum and θ_1, θ_2 and θ_3 read from the 2D NumPy array created in pre-processing. While this method is accurate, chaotic motion is not always as simple as predicting a single step; often, predicting multiple steps ahead is preferred (such as predicting brain waves of patients well into the future to prevent harm early) [23],[24]. Additionally, when this model is tested on an untrained condition, it will fail as the model is confined to prediction on this single angle. This approach captures local temporal dependencies but can struggle with large divergences or untrained initial conditions.

2) *Time-Step-Based:* Because of the constraints of the Sliding Window, we then proposed a new time-step-based

Fig. 5. Data preprocessing workflow. The system angles are solved via ODE-RK4 and stored in NumPy arrays, normalized, and then split into train/test sets for subsequent model ingestion.

Fig. 6. Neural network sliding window setup. The first 50 steps train the network to predict the 51st step (0-49 index). N (index of 2D array) = 0 initially.

approach that trained the model on a broader set of initial angles rather than a single initial angle to generalize to the system as a whole. To prevent overflow from the large number of angles (e.g. 30) the time interval was reduced from 1000s to 10s. Instead of directly predicting from an immediate history, we used all the data for training, and tested our model on a system with an **unknown/untrained initial condition** and predicted the entire 10s of motion rather than a single data point. This method generalizes better to interpolated initial angles unseen in training [25], allowing for the prediction of entirely new pendulum trajectories within the range of sampled

initial angles. To differentiate the many initial angles however, we needed to augment each training sample with additional features not included in the Sliding Window method:

- 1) The *current time index*, t .
- 2) The *initial angles*, $(\theta_1(0), \theta_2(0))$ or $(\theta_1(0), \theta_2(0), \theta_3(0))$.

while also keeping the angle(s) at the current time step, $\theta_1(t), \theta_2(t)$ (and $\theta_3(t)$ for triple pendulum). The timestep feature is used for the model to understand the relationship between time and position for a large set of initial angles, allowing it to learn and generalize to other systems. The initial angle was also fed as an input feature to allow the model to understand the relationship between initial angle and position, and be able to predict a new system within the range of initial conditions trained. This capability is particularly critical in bioinformatics applications such as predicting EEG signals over time or inferring future gene expression levels, where systems must generalize to unseen physiological conditions.

C. Models and Implementation

A total of ten machine learning and neural network models were developed:

- *Conventional ML Models*: Random Forest Regressor (RF) [26], Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) [27], and Autoregressive (AR).
- *Feedforward Networks*: Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) [28] and simple FFNN.
- *Recurrent Networks*: Vanilla RNN (VRNN) [29], LSTM, GRU [30], Bi-directional RNN (BiRNN) [31], and stacked RNNs.

For neural network implementations, PyTorch was used to handle tensor operations and GPU acceleration where available [32]. Learning rates were tuned conservatively (typically 10^{-3} – 10^{-4}) to prevent overfitting, and early stopping was employed based on validation loss. Each model trained on the normalized angle data (and optional friction parameter) for a fixed number of epochs (100–200), with mini-batches randomly sampled to facilitate convergence.

D. Evaluation Metrics and Protocol

We measured prediction quality using:

- Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE):

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2},$$

which emphasizes large errors and is well-suited to time-series comparisons.

- Coefficient of Determination (R^2):

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2}.$$

Higher R^2 indicates a stronger fit to the actual trajectory.

Time-series RMSE and R^2 metrics are commonly used in bioinformatics tasks such as forecasting biomarker fluctuations or modeling oscillatory gene cycles.

Training/Testing Splits:

- *Sliding Window*: First 50 data points solely for testing, rest of 9,999,950 points were trained and tested. No specific split (detailed above).
- *Time-Step-Based*: Of the multiple initial angles, all except one were used for training, reserving a subset (or an “in-between” initial angle) for test. This allowed rigorous testing on completely new conditions.

Fig. 7. Workflow for model training and testing, with final performance evaluation.

E. Stability Analysis (Lyapunov Exponents)

To further characterize chaotic regimes, we computed Lyapunov exponents by perturbing the initial angles slightly and tracking divergence over time:

$$\text{LyapExp} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \ln \left| \frac{\theta_{\text{pert}}(t) - \theta_{\text{base}}(t)}{\theta_{\text{pert}}(0) - \theta_{\text{base}}(0)} \right|.$$

Positive exponents confirm exponential divergence and thus chaos [11]. We also performed an eigenvalue-based stability check at key equilibrium points to confirm system characteristics (e.g., stable oscillation versus saddle-type instabilities) [33].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A crucial question in chaotic system modeling is whether machine learning techniques can capture the extreme sensitivity to initial conditions. Our approach tested both a *sliding window* and a *time-step-based* method using multiple models, including Random Forest (RF), MLP, AR, LSTM, GRU, VRNN, BiRNN, and others. We began with a single initial condition set (angles $[90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ for the double pendulum and $[90^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ for the triple pendulum) and then expanded to a broader distribution of angles under the time-step-based approach.

8A:

8B:

8C:

8D:

Fig. 8. (8A–8D) ODE-RK4 solution graphs of the double pendulum without friction. Angles vary from highly chaotic ($\theta_1 = 120^\circ, \theta_2 = 0^\circ$) to less chaotic ($\theta_1 = 0^\circ, \theta_2 = 120^\circ$).

A. Angle and Trajectory Analysis

Many groups like Chattopadhyay *et al.* [34] leverage deep neural networks for modeling chaotic system dynamics. These studies often employ single-layer or shallow architectures [35] and have partially explored multi-pendulum behavior [36]. In our initial exploration, we solved the double pendulum equations (frictionless) at various initial angles. We found that when $[\theta_1, \theta_2] \geq [89.1089^\circ, 59.6026^\circ]$, the pendulum exhibited fully rotating, high-chaos trajectories (Fig. 8A), whereas $[\theta_1, \theta_2] \leq [59.6026^\circ, 89.1089^\circ]$ yielded less chaotic, more single-pendulum-like motion (Fig. 8B). Our subsequent numerical experiments suggested θ_1 dominates chaos more strongly than θ_2 under frictionless conditions.

To examine friction, we introduced damping constants (damping1 and damping2 for the respective rods). As shown in Fig. 9, the influence of θ_2 on chaotic behavior becomes more pronounced with friction. Larger initial angles still induce chaos, but damping reduces the severity of the rotational flips (Fig. 9C–9D) relative to their frictionless counterparts.

Based on these findings, we initially trained models using a sliding window on $[90^\circ, 90^\circ]$, which balanced chaos and stability (over 0–1000 s). However, the massive 10M-point dataset was computationally heavy, especially when evaluating multiple initial angles. For a more generalized framework, we adopted a shorter time interval (0–10 s) at $\theta_1 = 120^\circ$ and varied $\theta_2 \in [0^\circ, 3^\circ]$ in increments of 0.1° . This procedure yielded 30 initial angles and 60,000 data points, plus additional “in-between” angles (e.g. $[120^\circ, 2.05^\circ]$) for testing.

B. Double Pendulum

Sliding Window Approach. Fig. 10 shows that under a single-angle, sliding-window configuration, LSTM reached an RMSE

Fig. 9. (9A–9D) Double pendulum with friction. Comparisons show how damping alters chaotic motion at various angle configurations.

Fig. 10. Sliding window results at $[\theta_1, \theta_2] = [90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ (no friction). LSTM achieves the lowest RMSE and highest R^2 .

of 5.75×10^{-5} and $R^2 \approx 0.999998$. GRU followed with an RMSE of 6.2×10^{-4} . Conventional ML methods (RF, AR) performed worse (RMSE in the range 10^{-2}). Although this approach yielded impressive short-term accuracy, it did not robustly generalize to different angles.

Time-Step Approach: Multiple Angles. Under frictionless conditions, training on angles $[120^\circ, 0^\circ] \dots [120^\circ, 3^\circ]$, LSTM secured an RMSE of 2.7×10^{-2} and $R^2 = 0.991$ on the trained angle (Fig. 11). However, at the unseen $[120^\circ, 2.05^\circ]$, RMSE rose to 0.26, reflecting the system’s high sensitivity in an undamped regime. Introducing friction stabilized predictions considerably (Fig. 12): LSTM recorded $R^2 = 0.9981$ and RMSE 9.5×10^{-3} on $[120^\circ, 0^\circ]$. Testing at $[120^\circ, 2.05^\circ]$ (Fig. 13) yielded RMSE 1.5×10^{-2} , indicating strong generalization.

Figs. 14–16 illustrate trajectory overlays for LSTM and VRNN under friction vs. no-friction scenarios. Notably, in frictionless systems (Fig. 14B), large deviations occur

Fig. 11. Time-step approach (no friction) for $\theta_1 = 120^\circ, \theta_2 = 0^\circ$. LSTM outperforms the other models on the known angle.

Fig. 12. Time-step approach (with friction) at $[120^\circ, 0^\circ]$. LSTM returns near-perfect $R^2 = 0.9981$ and RMSE 9.5×10^{-3} .

Fig. 13. Comparison of RMSE and R^2 on unseen angle $[120^\circ, 2.05^\circ]$ with friction. LSTM and VRNN remain robust.

when the model faces an untrained angle. Under friction (Figs. 15B, 16A–B), predictions stay close to the true trajectory, emphasizing how damping curbs chaos.

C. Triple Pendulum

For three-link systems, chaos intensifies with each additional degree of freedom. When $[\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3] \geq [94.737^\circ, 39.131^\circ, 33.333^\circ]$, we observed heightened instability. Conversely, angles below certain thresholds

Fig. 14. (14A,14B) LSTM trajectory (no friction). (A) known angle $[120^\circ, 0^\circ]$, (B) unseen angle $[120^\circ, 2.05^\circ]$. In figures 14, 15, 16, orange represents the actual trajectory and blue displays the predicted trajectory.

Fig. 15. (15A,15B) LSTM trajectory (with friction) for trained vs. "in-between" angle. Minimal deviation is observed in (B).

Fig. 16. (16A,16B) VRNN trajectory with friction. The model retains accuracy even for an untrained angle, though slightly less than LSTM.

Fig. 17. (17A,17B) Triple pendulum angle variations. (A) exhibits extensive chaos, (B) remains relatively stable.

produced more stable, single-pendulum-like arcs. Fig. 17 highlights two contrasting regimes, $[90^\circ, 60^\circ, 45^\circ]$ vs. $[45^\circ, 60^\circ, 90^\circ]$.

Sliding Window vs. Time-Step. Under a short sliding window, the Vanilla RNN gave an RMSE of 1.825×10^{-4} and $R^2 \approx 0.999999$, surpassing LSTM. This likely owes to the triple pendulum's rapid, localized fluctuations. In the

Fig. 18. (18A,18B) Triple Pendulum (no friction) across multiple angles. (18C,18D) friction-based testing on known vs. unseen angles.

Fig. 19. (19A,19B) Comparison of LSTM and GRU on friction-based triple pendulum. GRU slightly outperforms LSTM for unseen angles.

time-step approach (Figs. 18A,B), we again varied angles (e.g. $[120^\circ, 0^\circ, 0.1^\circ] \dots [120^\circ, 0^\circ, 3^\circ]$). GRU emerged with slightly better RMSE (1.688×10^{-1}) than LSTM (2.175×10^{-1}). Testing an unseen angle $[120^\circ, 0^\circ, 2.05^\circ]$ under friction (Fig. 18C,D) reinforced GRU's advantage, achieving $R^2 = 0.98823$ and RMSE 9.112×10^{-3} . LSTM still performed well, but GRU's simpler gating mechanism may be more robust for triple pendulum data.

Fig. 19 demonstrates how LSTM and GRU trajectories align with ground truth under friction. Both networks manage the additional link complexity, though GRU yields marginally lower RMSE.

Fig. 20. (20) Lyapunov exponent heatmap for initial conditions over 10 s. High positive exponents indicate strong chaos, near-zero or negative imply stability. Black box represents most stable initial angles.

Fig. 21. (21A,21B) Phase portraits around $(0^\circ, 0^\circ)$ (A) vs. $(180^\circ, 180^\circ)$ (B). The latter exhibits saddle-type eigenvalues, fueling instability.

D. Stability Analysis

Lyapunov Exponents. Fig. 20 shows a heatmap of Lyapunov exponents for the double pendulum. Regions with $\theta_1 > 120^\circ$ typically exhibit large positive exponents, confirming chaotic divergence. More stable angles yield near-zero or negative exponents, aligning with the limited flips we observed in trajectory plots. Such sensitivity maps may reflect system instability thresholds in biological systems like cardiac rhythms or gene expression cascades.

Eigenvalue Checks. Linearizing about $(0, 0)$ produces imaginary eigenvalues, indicative of undamped oscillation, while

$(180^\circ, 180^\circ)$ yields real eigenvalues revealing a saddle point. Phase-portrait simulations confirm that small perturbations at $(180^\circ, 180^\circ)$ grow over time, one hallmark of chaos in coupled pendulums (Fig. 21). Fig. 22 provides a consolidated look at RMSE across multiple angles and models, underscoring friction’s role in reducing errors within strongly chaotic regimes.

E. Discussion

Our work indicates that (1) recurrent neural networks, particularly LSTM and GRU, can capture the multi-pendulum’s chaotic trajectories well, and (2) incorporating friction fosters better generalization for unseen initial angles. Compared to older linear or shallow models, RNNs harness hidden states that encode sensitive dependence on initial conditions more effectively.

Given these findings, we believe the predictive architectures outlined here—particularly the LSTM-based framework—could be adapted to real biological systems where sensitive dependence on initial molecular or electrical states drives disease progression or treatment outcomes. Applications may include epileptic seizure forecasting, modeling of circadian rhythms, or real-time biofeedback systems in closed-loop therapeutics

Overall, our time-step-based approach addresses some of the limitations of classic sliding window methods, proving especially effective under moderate chaos with friction damping. These lessons extend to broader domains where non-linear feedback drives sensitive transitions, including certain gene regulatory circuits, oscillatory enzyme kinetics, and multi-drug synergy studies [38]. In such scenarios, adopting friction-like damping terms or carefully constructed initial condition sets may similarly enhance model robustness and predictive power.

F. Limitations

Although our results are impactful, we note several constraints. First, our models are limited based on the number of variables at play. The computational cost grows significantly with the number of pendulum arms or when simulating real-world biological systems with many interdependent variables, due to an increased number of features. Scaling this framework to model such high-dimensional chaotic systems will require further optimization and possibly hybrid modeling strategies.” Second, real-world data often contain noise and parameter variability not reflected in these idealized simulations like differential equations and RK4. Third, advanced hyperparameter tuning (e.g., for LSTM cell sizes or GRU gating rates) may further improve performance [37]. Lastly, many constants were not changed at all throughout the study; a further investigation on this may reveal new results. Future extensions might explore multi-scale modeling or domain-specific transformations to reduce computational demands.

IV. CONCLUSION

Our investigation demonstrates that time-step-based neural networks, especially RNN variants such as LSTM and GRU,

Fig. 22. (22) Heatmaps of all Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values for the models and networks coded with the new method. The lighter the box, the greater the RMSE and the darker the box, the lower the RMSE.

can capture the sensitive dependence on initial conditions that defines chaotic behavior in multi-pendulum systems. By systematically comparing these methods under both frictional and frictionless conditions, we established that LSTM offers high predictive accuracy for double pendula, whereas GRU performs robustly for triple pendula. We further showed that incorporating physical realism (e.g., friction) significantly improves model generalization to unseen initial angles, underlining the value of damping in stabilizing highly chaotic trajectories.

Non-linear, multi-factor biological systems, such as regulatory networks involved in drug metabolism or cancer progression, can exhibit chaotic transitions akin to the pendulum’s sensitive dependence on initial conditions. In drug discovery, small variations in compound concentration can lead to drastically different outcomes in combinatorial therapies. The methods we present here—particularly the time-step-based RNN approach—offer a blueprint for forecasting the evolution of such systems, enabling researchers to identify critical thresholds or “tipping points” in pharmacological interventions. Further, Lyapunov exponent and eigenvalue analyses, commonly employed to gauge chaos in mechanical systems, can serve as powerful analogs for stability analyses in biochemical networks, aiding in the design of robust, targeted therapies.

The multi-pendulum framework we’ve developed offers robust parallels to various biological systems characterized

by nonlinear oscillatory behavior. In neural dynamics, for instance, our time-step-based LSTM approach closely resembles methodologies that have successfully captured chaotic neural oscillations in EEG recordings, where initial conditions analogous to pendulum angles represent baseline neural states [39]. Similarly, our networks’ performance on chaotic pendulum trajectories mirrors their effectiveness in predicting cardiac arrhythmias [40], where small variations in initial heart rate conditions can lead to drastically different outcomes—just as with pendulum angles. The friction parameter we incorporated serves as an analogue to biological damping mechanisms in gene regulatory networks [42], where long term short memory networks trained on synthetic gene expression data have demonstrated how initial expression levels can determine future oscillatory states. These parallels strengthen the case that our chaos prediction methodology provides a broadly applicable framework for understanding complex biological systems with sensitive dependence on initial conditions. Bridging these two worlds reinforces the interdisciplinary nature of chaos modeling and supports broader applications in computational biology, personalized medicine, and real-time therapeutic monitoring.

Our results indicate that even with relatively constrained computational resources, it is possible to make reliable forecasts of chaotic motion across multiple pendulum arms. Future research could expand to larger, more complex pendulum chains or other nonlinear systems such as the Lorenz attractor [41]. Additionally, systematically introducing noise into the training data or incorporating real-world measurements would help validate model resilience to measurement perturbations. Exploring hyperparameter tuning strategies specific to recurrent networks [39] may further enhance predictive accuracy. Finally, integrating domain-specific constraints or multi-scale modeling techniques could broaden these applications.

ELECTRONIC SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Additional materials, including derivations of the triple pendulum equations and code, are available in the Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI). Please access the CTNN ESI at: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1iVMZ4JdpAY_9n0kCuJ4ElmJUyoDr9cjo/view?usp=sharing

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data and code is available in the GitHub repositories at DOIs: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15093035>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15093037>

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank the Aspiring Scholars Directed Research Program (ASDRP) for fostering this collaboration and providing valuable resources. We are grateful to Ved Vyas for implementing the autoregressive and feedforward neural network models for the double pendulum. We thank Joshveer Singh for training the random forest and LSTM models for the triple pendulum, and for contributing source analysis. Special thanks to Arnab

Bansal for his early contributions to the friction models and initial analysis of the double pendulum.

We also thank Huifang Qin, Professor of Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence at the ASDRP Department of Computer Science and Engineering, and Professor Robert Downing, Chair Emeritus of the ASDRP Department of Computer Science and former Professor of Computer Science and Astrophysics and Engineering, for their thorough review and valuable feedback on this manuscript.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bishop, R. (2015). Chaos (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy). <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/chaos/>
- [2] Climate of chaos: Why warming makes weather less predictable — Stanford Doerr School of Sustainability. (2021, December 14). <https://sustainability.stanford.edu/news/climate-chaos-why-warming-makes-weather-less-predictable>
- [3] Kliuchnikov, I., Sigova, M., & Beizerov, N. (2017). Chaos Theory in Finance. *Procedia Computer Science*, 119, 368–375.
- [4] Halloran, J. P., & Erdemir, A. (2011). Adaptive Surrogate Modeling for Expedited Estimation of Nonlinear Tissue Properties Through Inverse Finite Element Analysis. *Annals of Biomedical Engineering*, 39(9), 2388–2397.
- [5] Sensitivity to Initial Conditions in Chaos - Wolfram Demonstrations Project. (n.d.). <https://demonstrations.wolfram.com/SensitivityToInitialConditionsInChaos/>
- [6] Arslan Basharat, & Shah, M. (2009). *Time Series Prediction by Chaotic Modeling of Nonlinear Dynamical Systems*.
- [7] Flight chaos made worse by engineer delay, report finds. (2024, March 14). <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-68563068>
- [8] Jain, H., Ranjan, A., & Gupta, K. (2013). Analysis of Chaos in Double Pendulum. In *Proc. of ICETET*, 26, 171–176.
- [9] (2019). Motion of a Triple Rod Pendulum. *Authorea*.
- [10] cloud4science. (2021, February 28). Deep Learning with Real Data and the Chaotic Double Pendulum. <https://cloud4scieng.org/2021/02/28/deep-learning-with-real-data-and-the-chaotic-double-pendulum/>
- [11] Yesilyurt, B. (2019). *Equations of Motion Formulation of a Pendulum Containing N-point Masses*. arXiv:1910.12610
- [12] Runge-Kutta Method - an overview — ScienceDirect Topics. (n.d.). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/mathematics/runge-kutta-method>
- [13] Lin, D. C., & Rymer, W. Z. (2000). Damping Actions of the Neuromuscular System With Inertial Loads: Soleus Muscle of the Decerebrate Cat. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 83(2), 652–658. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.2000.83.2.652>
- [14] LSTM — PyTorch 2.5 documentation. (2023). <https://pytorch.org/docs/stable/generated/torch.nn.LSTM.html>
- [15] Autoregressive Model - an overview — ScienceDirect Topics. (n.d.). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/neuroscience/autoregressive-model>
- [16] Binghamton University, State University of New York. (2024). Lyapunov Exponent. In *Introduction to the Modeling and Analysis of Complex Systems*. <https://math.libretexts.org/@go/page/7819>
- [17] Friction Force - an overview — ScienceDirect Topics. (n.d.). <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/friction-force>
- [18] AWREJCEWICZ, J., KUDRA, G., & LAMARQUE, C.-H. (2004). INVESTIGATION OF TRIPLE PENDULUM WITH IMPACTS USING FUNDAMENTAL SOLUTION MATRICES. *International Journal of Bifurcation and Chaos*, 14(12), 4191–4213. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218127404011818>
- [19] numpy.array — NumPy v2.1 Manual. (2024). <https://numpy.org/doc/2.1/reference/generated/numpy.array.html>
- [20] scikit-learn. (2019). `sklearn.preprocessing.MinMaxScaler` — scikit-learn 0.22.1 documentation. Scikit-Learn.org. <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.preprocessing.MinMaxScaler.html>
- [21] Shkadinsky, K. G., & Rogachev, A. S. (2017). Chaotic Regimes (p. 65). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-804173-4.00027-2>
- [22] Chu, C.-S. J. (1995). Time series segmentation: A sliding window approach. *Information Sciences*, 85(1–3), 147–173.
- [23] Banitalebi, A., Setarehdan, S. K., & Hossein-Zadeh, G. A. (2009). A technique based on chaos for brain computer interfacing. 2009 14th International CSI Computer Conference, 464–469. <https://doi.org/10.1109/csicc.2009.5349623>
- [24] Song, J. U., Choi, K., & Kahng, B. (2021). Machine learning approaches for Kuramoto coupled oscillator systems. ArXiv.org. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.08918>
- [25] Hong, D., Wang, J., & Gardner, R. (2005b). Orthonormal Wavelet Bases. Elsevier EBooks, 209–269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-012354861-0/50007-5>
- [26] `sklearn.ensemble.RandomForestClassifier` — scikit-learn 0.20.3 documentation. (2018). <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.ensemble.RFC>
- [27] `SGDRegressor`. (2024). Scikit-Learn. https://scikit-learn.org/1.5/modules/generated/sklearn.linear_model.SGDRegressor
- [28] `sklearn.neural_network.MLPRegressor` — scikit-learn 0.21.3 documentation. (2010). https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.neural_network.MLPRegressor
- [29] GeeksforGeeks. (2018, October 3). Introduction to Recurrent Neural Network - GeeksforGeeks. GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/introduction-to-recurrent-neural-network/>
- [30] Gated Recurrent Unit Networks. (2019, July 9). GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/gated-recurrent-unit-networks/>
- [31] Bidirectional Recurrent Neural Network. (2023, June 8). GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/bidirectional-recurrent-neural-network/>
- [32] NVIDIA CUDA-X. (2011, October 6). NVIDIA Developer. <https://developer.nvidia.com/gpu-accelerated-libraries>
- [33] Xie, D., Wang, X., Zhang, Y., & Gu, C. (2023). Introduction. Elsevier EBooks, 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-323-99748-5.00001-6>
- [34] Chattopadhyay, A., Hassanzadeh, P., & Subramanian, D. (2020). Data-driven predictions of a multiscale Lorenz 96 chaotic system using machine-learning methods: Reservoir Computing, Artificial Neural Network, and Long Short-Term Memory Network. *Nonlinear Processes in Geophysics*, 27(3), 373–389.
- [35] GeeksforGeeks. (2024, October 9). Shallow Neural Networks. GeeksforGeeks. <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/shallow-neural-networks/>
- [36] Harvard University. (n.d.). Chaotic Pendulum. <https://sciencedemonstrations.fas.harvard.edu/presentations/chaotic-pendulum>
- [37] Saravanakumar Sengottaiyan, Sathiyamurthy Subbarayan, Viswanathan, V., & Pathmanaban Pugazhendi. (2024). Optimized machine learning with hyperparameter tuning and response surface methodology for predicting tribological performance in bio-composite materials. *Polymer Composites*, 45(10), 9421–9439. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pc.28418>
- [38] Seron, M. M., & Goodwin, G. C. (1999). Sensitivity limitations in nonlinear feedback control. *Systems & Control Letters*, 27(4), 249–254. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-6911\(95\)00058-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-6911(95)00058-5)
- [39] Cestnik, R., & Abel, M. (2019). Inferring the dynamics of oscillatory systems using recurrent neural networks. *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science*, 29(6), 063128. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5096918>
- [40] Maie Aboghazalah, Passent El-kafrawy, Ahmed, A. M., Rasha Elnemr, Belgacem Bouallegue, & Ayman El-sayed. (2024). Arrhythmia Detection by Using Chaos Theory with Machine Learning Algorithms. *Computers, Materials & Continua/Computers, Materials & Continua (Print)*, 79(3), 3855–3875. <https://doi.org/10.32604/cmc.2023.039936>
- [41] VOHRADSKY, J. (2001). Neural network model of gene expression. *The FASEB Journal*, 15(3), 846–854. <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.00-0361.com>
- [42] Tucker, W. (1999). The Lorenz attractor exists. *Comptes Rendus de l'Académie Des Sciences - Series I - Mathematics*, 328(12), 1197–1202. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0764-4442\(99\)80439-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0764-4442(99)80439-x)